

NFM Glossary

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https://www.lancaster.ac.uk/lec/sites/qnfm/NFM_Glossary_NERC_NFM_programme.xlsx

Table 1 Hydrological processes

Table	Term, definition and [source]
1	Actual Evapotranspiration The rate of evapotranspiration from a surface or vegetation canopy to the atmosphere under the prevailing meteorological conditions and water availability [Beven, 2012]. Evapotranspiration includes wet-canopy evaporation (interception loss) and transpiration. See also Potential Evaporation
1	Advection Transport with the velocity in a flow pathway. Often used to refer to transport with the mean velocity of the flow within some control volume (see also Dispersion) [Beven, 2012]
1	Aerodynamic Resistance Scaling parameter for sensible and latent heat fluxes in Penman–Monteith equation [Beven, 2012]
1	Antecedent Conditions The state of wetness of a catchment prior to an event or period of simulation [Beven, 2012]
1	Atmospheric Demand The rate of potential evapotranspiration for given atmospheric conditions of temperature, humidity and wind speed without any limit due to the availability of water [Beven, 2012]. See Potential Evapotranspiration
1	Canopy Resistance An effective resistance to the transport of water vapour from leaf stomata to the atmosphere [Beven, 2012]
1	Capillary potential See Head
1	Catchment The area of land draining to a point on the channel network, normally the location of the stream gauging station. See Drainage Basin and Watershed
1	Catchment leakage The component of rainfall that does not leave the defined Catchment by evapotranspiration or through the channel gauging station, but instead leaves the defined Catchment as subsurface flow. See Catchment
1	Celerity or Wave Speed. The speed with which a disturbance of pressure propagates through the flow domain [Beven, 2012]

- 1 **Coefficient of Permeability** See Saturated hydraulic conductivity
- 1 **Contributing area** A term used in a variety of ways in hydrology. Most often it refers to the dynamic part of the catchment contributing either surface or rapid subsurface flows to the storm hydrograph [adapted from Beven, 2012]+C24
- 1 **Diffusivity** The product of unsaturated hydraulic conductivity and the gradient of the curve relating capillary potential to soil moisture content [Beven, 2012]
- 1 **Dispersion** Variation in the transport of water or other quantity as a result of variation in flow velocity within some control volume. This may be a result of variations in velocity within a particular pathway or of variations across multiple pathways as a result of heterogeneity in the characteristics of different pathways. The latter is often referred to as macrodispersion (see also Advection) [Beven, 2012]
- 1 **Drainage Basin** See Catchment
- 1 **Dry bulk density** The dry mass of soil in an undisturbed volume of soil
- 1 **Effective Storage Capacity** The difference between the current moisture in the soil immediately above the water table and saturation [Beven, 2012]
- 1 **Environmental Tracer** A tracer for water flow through a hillslope or catchment system that occurs naturally in the environment. Oxygen and hydrogen isotopes are the most commonly used environmental tracers because they are part of the water molecule, but other tracers are also used [Beven, 2012]
- 1 **Ephemeral Stream** A stream that only flows during storm periods; they occur in Zero-order basins. See Perennial stream
- 1 **Evapotranspiration** See Actual evapotranspiration
- 1 **Field Capacity** An imprecisely defined variable normally expressed as the water content of the soil when it is allowed to drain from saturation until rapid drainage has ceased (see Soil Moisture Deficit) [Beven, 2012]
- 1 **Head** An expression of pressure often expressed as energy per unit weight in hydrology and hydraulics since it has units of length [adapted from Beven, 2012]. Also called Pressure potential and Capillary potential (and sometimes in unsaturated soils Matric Potential)

- 1 **Hortonian overland flow** See Infiltration-excess overland flow
- 1 **Hydraulic Geometry** Expresses the relationships between river discharge and channel width and depth and flow velocity at a point and with changing scale in the river network [Woo, 2012]
- 1 **Hydraulic Roughness** See Roughness (hillslope surface or channel)
- 1 **Hydraulic Storage** Storage retained in river channel as discharge is withheld by blockage or retardation of flow [Woo, 2012]
- 1 **Hysteretic function** A function between two hydrological variables that is different under wetting and drying conditions. Might refer to storage–discharge at the catchment scale or relationship between moisture content and capillary potential in soils [adapted from Beven, 2012]
- 1 **Infiltration** The movement of water into the ground surface. See Percolation
- 1 **Infiltration Capacity** The effective saturated hydraulic conductivity at the ground surface. In the field this may be less than that for a fully saturated sample because of air entrapment effects. See Infiltrometer
- 1 **Infiltration-excess overland flow** Overland flow generated when rainfall intensity exceeds the saturated hydraulic conductivity of the ground surface; sometimes abbreviated to IOF. See Saturated hydraulic conductivity, Infiltration capacity and Saturation overland flow
- 1 **Interception loss** See Wet-canopy evaporation
- 1 **Macropores** Large pores in the soil that may form important pathways for infiltration and redistribution of water bypassing the soil matrix as a preferential flow [Beven, 2012] Longer and larger diameter macropores may be called Natural soil pipes
- 1 **Manning's n** A coefficient of roughness, used in a formula for estimating the capacity of a channel or a pipe to convey water [NEH, 2012]
- 1 **Natural soil pipes** See Macropores

- 1 **Net precipitation** The component of the gross precipitation that penetrates a vegetation canopy by either Throughfall or Stemflow. The component of the gross precipitation that does not reach the ground but is returned to the atmosphere is called the Wet-canopy evaporation
- 1 **Overland Flow** Water flow on hillslopes (as opposed to within Perennial channels) resulting from infiltration-excess or saturation (including return-flow) mechanisms. See Infiltration-excess overland flow, Return-flow and Saturation overland flow
- 1 **Percolation** The movement of water within the subsurface. See Infiltration
- 1 **Perennial Stream** A stream that flows continuously throughout most years; they are first-order or higher channels. See Ephemeral stream
- 1 **Porosity** The volume of pore space in an undisturbed volume of soil
- 1 **Potential evapotranspiration** Wet-canopy evaporation and transpiration from vegetation surfaces with no limitation due to water availability (see also Atmospheric demand) [adapted from Beven, 2012] see Actual Evaporation
- 1 **Preferential flow** Local concentrations of flow in the soil that may be due to the effects of macropores, local variations in hydraulic properties or fingering of a wetting front moving into the soil profile (see also Macropores) [Beven, 2012]
- 1 **Pressure potential** See Head
- 1 **Recession Flow** Discharge that falls from peakflow until the flow is raised by a subsequent hydrograph rise event [Woo, 2012]
- 1 **Return-Flow** Where subsurface flow returns to the ground surface before reaching a channel
- 1 **Riparian Area** The part of the catchment that is immediately adjacent to a permanent natural watercourse [adapted from Beven, 2012] See also Perennial stream
- 1 **Roughness (hillslope surface or channel)** The hydraulic roughness is a measure of the amount of frictional resistance water flow experiences passing over a hillslope surface or down a perennial channel. Example measures of roughness are Manning's Roughness Coefficient (n) and Chézy's Coefficient (C).

- 1 **Runoff** An ambiguous term that can be used to mean: (1) flow in perennial channels (2) Channel flow per unit catchment area, (3) Overland flow on hillslopes (Infiltration-excess overland flow or Saturation overland flow), or (4) rapid subsurface flow (see also Throughflow or Subsurface stormflow). Note: Surface runoff is equally ambiguous and may mean: (1) overland flow plus channel flow (Horton, 1933 p446), (2) channel flow only (Hursh, 1936 p302) or (3) overland flow only (Synder,1939 p736)
- 1 **Runoff Coefficient** The proportion of the rainfall depth that appears in the channel flow (as a ratio of volumes; or per unit catchment area, as a ratio of depth equivalent outputs to inputs)
- 1 **Runoff Generation Mechanisms** The pathways by which rainfall reaches channels; often with a focus on the fast pathways producing the storm hydrograph
- 1 **Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity** The flow of subsurface water per unit hydraulic gradient and unit cross-sectional area when the subsurface media is fully saturated with water (equivalent to Coefficient of Permeability).
- 1 **Saturation Overland Flow** Where subsurface flow returns to the ground surface before reaching a channel (by a mechanism called Return-flow) it may then flow over this saturated ground to the channel. Any precipitation falling directly on this saturated soil will also contribute to this overland flow. The saturated hydraulic conductivity of the ground surface in these saturated may be greater than the rainfall intensity [Shaw et al., 2010] See Infiltration-excess overland flow and Return-flow
- 1 **Soil Moisture Content** The amount of water held in the soil expressed either (1) with reference to mass of dry soil (mass wetness), (2) volume of pore space within an undisturbed soil (volumetric moisture content, or volumetric wetness eg BS1377-3: 1990), or (3) as a proportion of the porosity (saturation wetness) [Shaw et al., 2010]
- 1 **Soil Moisture Deficit (SMD)** A state variable used in many hydrological models as an expression of soil water storage below either field capacity or saturation. It is usually expressed in units of depth of water [Beven, 2012]
- 1 **Soil Moisture Characteristic Curve** A function relating soil moisture content to capillary potential [adapted from Beven, 2012]
- 1 **Specific Moisture Capacity** The gradient of the curve relating unsaturated soil moisture content to capillary potential [Beven, 2012] See Soil Moisture Content and Capillary Potential
- 1 **Stemflow** Rainfall that reaches the ground via the stems of plants [Beven, 2012] See Net Precipitation
- 1 **Surface Runoff** An ambiguous term that may mean: (1) overland flow plus channel flow (Horton, 1933 p446), (2) channel flow only (Hursh, 1936 p302) or (3) overland flow only (Synder,1939 p736)

- 1 **Throughfall** Rainfall that reaches the ground by (1) falling through gaps in a vegetation canopy, and (3) being intercepted by leaves and branches and then dripping to the ground [Beven, 2012] See Net Precipitation
- 1 **Throughflow** Often used for rapid near-surface downslope subsurface flow in the soil profile [Beven, 2012]
- 1 **Transit Time Distributions** (also called Travel Time Distributions) The distribution of times taken by water to move through a hillslope, channel network or catchment. Used to indicate both the transit or travel times for an increment of input to reach an outlet and the transit or travel times for an increment of discharge to reach the outlet. These are different and should be properly differentiated (see also Residence Time Distributions) [Beven, 2012]
- 1 **Transpiration** The evaporation from water from within plant stomata. See also Actual Evapotranspiration and Wet-canopy evaporation
- 1 **Uniform Flow** An open channel flow or overland flow in which the slope of the water surface is equal to the bed slope such that energy loss due to frictional shear stress is exactly matched by the potential energy gain as the water moves downhill [Beven, 2012]
- 1 **Unsaturated Hydraulic Conductivity curve** The relationship between hydraulic conductivity and the Capillary potential, where the maximum value is the Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity
- 1 **Watershed** In USA, equivalent to term Catchment or Drainage Basin. In the UK, a watershed is the edge of the Catchment. See Catchment
- 1 **Wave speed** see Celerity.
- 1 **Wet-canopy evaporation** The evaporation from wetted vegetation surfaces (also called 'Interception loss'). See also Actual Evapotranspiration and Transpiration

Table 2 Measurement kit or methods

Table	Term, definition and [source]
2	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) A method of measuring instantaneous values of channel velocity (for calculation of channel discharge) using the Doppler effect of sound waves scattered back from particles suspended in the channel flow
2	Automatic weather station A collection of meteorological instruments (eg raingauge, net radiometer, anemometer, temperature and relative humidity sensor) connected to a common datalogger for automatic measurements at a sub-daily frequency
2	Current meter A method of measuring instantaneous values of channel velocity (for calculation of channel discharge) using either an impeller device and revolution counter or electromagnetic principles
2	Dilution gauging A method of measuring instantaneous value channel discharge using the two-component mixing equation and a conservative tracer (eg Rhodamine WT, sodium chloride)
2	Dip meter A device for manually measuring the depth of water (and hence Head) in a piezometer. See Head and Piezometer
2	Eddy Correlation Method A technique for measuring actual evapotranspiration (latent heat flux) as the product of rapid (>30 Hz) measurements of humidity and upward wind speed. Also called Eddy Covariance Method or Eddy Flux Method
2	Flume (control structure) A device installed on a watercourse to generate critical flow via constriction to develop a unique relationship between water level in the watercourse (stage) and the channel discharge
2	Gerlach trough A device for catching overland flow typically at a bounded experimental plot, for subsequent redirection into a measuring device (eg tipping-bucket and count datalogger)
2	Gravimetric method of soil moisture content determination A method whereby soil samples are dried in the oven and the loss of weight used to determine the Soil Moisture Content
2	Infiltrometer A device for measuring the Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity at the ground surface, the Infiltration Capacity. See Permeameter

- 2 **Permeameter** A device for measuring the Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity (also called Coefficient of Permeability) of subsurface media
- 2 **Permeameter** A device for measuring the Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity (also called Coefficient of Permeability) of subsurface media
- 2 **Piezometer** A device for measuring positive values of Capillary potential or Head at a point at the base of the unit connected to the surrounding media. Tests for Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity may be undertaken using these devices. See Capillary potential, Head and Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity
- 2 **Pressure transducer** A device for measuring pressure with a DC mV voltage output. It may be used to measure water level at a gauging station within a watercourse or lake, or water-level in a piezometer or pressure within a tensiometer. See Pressure transmitter
- 2 **Pressure transmitter** A device for measuring pressure with a 4-20 mA current output (and so not affected by the issues with pressure transducers). See Pressure transducer
- 2 **Raingauge or rain gauge** A device for measuring rainfall daily or monthly totals (using a storage raingauge) or sub-daily intensities (using an automatic raingauge)
- 2 **Sand (tension) table** A device for measuring Soil Moisture Characteristic Curve for undisturbed samples relatively wet subsurface media
- 2 **Shaft encoder** A device commonly used for measuring water level at national gauging stations where the turns of a pulley wheel (connected to a float-and-counterweight) are converted to digital output
- 2 **Slope-Area Method** Method of measuring a peak discharge after a flood event using one of the uniform flow equations by estimating the cross-sectional area, water surface slope and roughness coefficient at a site [Beven, 2012]
- 2 **Stilling well** A vertical pipe tapping the throat of a flume or upstream of a flume or weir used to still high frequency fluctuations in water level. It is needed where float-and-counter-weight devices used, and may be needed where other devices such as pressure transmitters are used
- 2 **Tensiometer** A device for measuring positive and negative values of Capillary potential. See Capillary potential
- 2 **Throughfall trough** A device for collecting Throughfall beneath a vegetation canopy. See Throughfall and Net precipitation

- 2 **Throughflow trough** A device for collecting lateral flows of water within the soil profile. See Gerlach trough for overland flow measurement
- 2 **Tipping-bucket mechanism** Typically a double-bucket device (with a magnet and reed switch connected to a counter or datalogger) using within some automatic raingauges or overland flow collectors
- 2 **Time Domain Reflectometry method of soil moisture content determination** A method whereby the moisture content around a wave guide attenuates an electromagnetic (EM) wave by changing the dielectric constant. At GHz frequencies, the dielectric constant is primarily affected by the soil moisture content. Simplified TDR devices operating at MHz frequencies are more often used
- 2 **Total station** A device for surveying the topography or location of features or instruments combining an Electronic Theodolite and a laser device for Electronic Distance Measurement (EDM)
- 2 **Weir (control structure)** A device installed on a watercourse to generate critical flow via fall to develop a unique relationship between water level in the watercourse (stage) and the channel discharge

Table 3 Modelling

Table	Term, definition and [source]
3	Automatic Optimisation Calibration of model parameters using a computer algorithm to maximise or minimise the value of an objective function [Beven, 2012]
3	Autocorrelated Errors A time series of model residuals that are not independent at each time step, i.e. that exhibit statistical correlation at one or more time steps apart [Beven, 2012]
3	Baseflow The component of a storm hydrograph below an arbitrary but fixed separation line; it may be the component of the storm hydrograph linearly related to storm rainfall. Also sometimes called 'direct runoff' or 'stormflow' See Quickflow and Baseflow Separation
3	Baseflow Separation A procedure associated with use of the unit hydrograph to separate the hydrograph into Quickflow and Baseflow components. Many different methods are available, mostly without any firm process basis [adapted from Beven, 2012]
3	Basis Functions Interpolation functions used in representing the variation of a predicted variable within each element of a finite element solution [Beven, 2012]
3	Behavioural Simulation A simulation that gives an acceptable reproduction of any observations available for model evaluation. Simulations that are not acceptable are nonbehavioural [Beven, 2012]
3	Big Leaf Assumption The representation of a vegetation canopy in predicting evapotranspiration as if it was a uniform surface [Beven, 2012]
3	Black Box Model A model that relates an input to a predicted output by a mathematical function or functions without any attempt to describe the processes controlling the response of the system [Beven, 2012] Also called Data-Based Model
3	Blind Validation Evaluation of a model using parameter values estimated before the modeller has seen any output data [Beven, 2012]
3	Boundary Conditions Constraints and values of variables required to run a model for a particular flow domain and time period. May include input variables, such as rainfall and temperatures, or constraints, such as specifying a fixed head (Dirichlet boundary condition) or impermeable boundary (Neumann boundary condition) or specified flux rate (Cauchy boundary condition) [Beven, 2012]

- 3 **Baseline** A set of initial or critical observations or data used for comparison and control [Sharp, 2016]
- 3 **Calibration** The process of adjusting parameter values of a model to obtain a better fit between observed and predicted variables. May be done manually or using an automatic calibration algorithm [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Closure Problem** The problem of estimating boundary fluxes for a discrete calculation unit in part of the flow domain when the appropriate relationships should be state and scale dependent [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Cloud Computing** The use of methods and data storage available via the Internet without the user having to worry about where computations are made or information is stored. These are becoming increasingly sophisticated and can provide elements that can be integrated with hydrological modelling (e.g. the use of GoogleMaps and GoogleView in visualisation of model results) [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Conceptual Model** A simplified model incorporating a Perceptual Model (eg hydrological mechanisms or processes) defined in the form of mathematical equations [Beven, 2012] See also Perceptual Model
- 3 **Catchment** The drainage area that collects water feeding into a stream, river, or lake [Cronan, 2018]
- 3 **Coupled Model** Any two or more models which work independently but are linked at set time intervals to provide mutual feedbacks [Troccoli et al., 2008]
- 3 **Data Assimilation** The process of using observational data to update model predictions (see also Real-Time Forecasting and Updating) [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Data-Based Model** See Black Box Model
- 3 **Data-Based Mechanistic (DBM) Modelling** An approach to modelling input–output systems (often using linear transfer functions) where possible model structures are identified as Data-Based Models, with some rejected on the basis of inconsistency with the [hydrological] processes or mechanisms. See Data-Based Model and Black-Box Model
- 3 **Deterministic Model** A model that, with a set of initial and boundary conditions, has only one possible outcome or prediction [Beven, 2012]

- 3 **Direct runoff** See Quickflow
- 3 **Disinformation** Used to describe observational data that might be used in calibrating a model but which is inconsistent as a result of measurement or other errors and therefore might not be informative in identifying a good model of the system [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Distributed Model** A model that predicts values of state variables varying in space (and normally time) [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Digital elevation model** A digital representation of a topographic surface. Abbreviated DEM [NEH, 2012]
- 3 **Downscaling** The translation of a forecast from one spatial and/or temporal resolution to a finer resolution. In spatial downscaling, the term is frequently applied to the translation of a forecast from a gridded average to a local point [Troccoli et al., 2008]
- 3 **Effective Rainfall** A part of the storm rainfall inputs to a catchment that is equivalent in volume to the Quickflow part of the hydrograph [adapted from Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Ensemble Predictions** A set of simulations based on running multiple models with different parameter sets or initial conditions. Used in weather forecasting, climate change predictions and uncertainty estimation [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Equifinality** The concept that there may be many models of a catchment that are acceptably consistent with the observations available [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Evaluation** see Validation
- 3 **Explicit Solution** The independent calculation of predicted variables at a time step given values of the variables at the previous time step (see also Implicit solution) [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Finite Difference Method** The approximate representation of a time or space differential in terms of variables separated by discrete increments in time or space [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Finite Element Method** The approximate representation of time or space differentials in terms of integrals of simple interpolation functions involving variables defined at nodes of an irregular discretisation of the flow domain into elements [Beven, 2012]

- 3 **Gain** A multiplier applied to a transfer function to scale inputs to outputs in a linear systems analysis. May be made adaptive in real-time forecasting [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Geomorphological Unit Hydrograph** A unit hydrograph derived from the structural relationships of the catchment geomorphology, in particular the branching structure of the channel network [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Global optimum** A set of parameter values that gives the best fit possible to a set of observations [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **HEC-RAS** A hydraulic model developed by the United States Army Corps of Engineers that solves the full dynamic 1-D Saint Venant Equation using an implicit, finite difference method.
- 3 **Hydrological Response Unit** A parcel of the land surface defined in terms of its soil, vegetation and topographic characteristics [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Hyperparameter** Used to describe the parameters of a structural model of the rainfall–runoff model residuals in statistical calibration of the rainfall–runoff model parameters (see also Model Inadequacy Function). Hyperparameters are estimated as part of the calibration process [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Implicit Solution** The simultaneous solution of predicted variables at a time step given values of the variables at the previous time step, usually by an iterative method (see also Explicit solution) [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Incommensurate** Used here to refer to variables or parameters with the same name that refer to different quantities because of a change in scale [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Initial Conditions** Values of storage or pressure variables required to initialise a model at the start of a simulation period [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Instrumentalism** Approach to science based on the pragmatic concept that empirical adequacy is sufficient to justify a model or theory. In rainfall–runoff modelling, this is equivalent to saying that a model that gives a good fit to observations in calibration should be useful in prediction, regardless of its theoretical underpinning [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Inverse Method** Model calibration by adjusting parameter values to reduce the differences between observations and predicted variables [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **JFLOW** A 2D hydraulic model that solves the shallow water equations using graphics processors (or GPUs) to perform the calculations

- 3 **Land Surface model** A Model used to calculate water and energy fluxes (and often carbon fluxes) between the land surface and the atmosphere in numerical weather prediction and climate models [adapted from Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Lead Time** The required time for a forecast ahead of the current time in real-time flood forecasting [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Linear Store** A model component in which the output is directly proportional to the current storage value. The basic building block of the general linear transfer function model and the Nash cascade [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Lumped Model** A model that treats the whole of a catchment as a single accounting unit and predicts only values of variables averaged over the catchment area [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Monte Carlo simulation** Simulation involving multiple runs of a model using different randomly chosen sets of parameter values [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Model discretization** The way in which the domain being modelled is described spatially. Can range from very high resolution 3-D spatial representations, to treating the region of Earth modeled as a complete single unit [adapted from Ogden, 2020]
- 3 **Model forcing** The inputs that drive a hydrologic model. These almost always include precipitation, and can include solar radiation, and other meteorological variables such as wind, temperature, and relative humidity, and external sources of water that flow across model domain boundaries such as runoff, wind- or tidal-driven water, or groundwater flow [adapted from Ogden, 2020]
- 3 **Muskingum-Cunge** A flood routing technique that applies to channel or reach routing [NEH, 2012]
- 3 **MODFLOW** A finite-difference numerical model for groundwater flow that was developed by the U.S. Geological Survey [Sharp, 2006]
- 3 **Network Width Function** A histogram of the number of reaches in the channel network at a given distance from the catchment outlet. Can be used as the basis for both linear and nonlinear flow routing algorithms [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Nonbehavioural Simulation** see Behavioural Simulation
- 3 **Nonlinear** A model is nonlinear if the outputs are not in direct proportion to the inputs but may vary with intensity or volume of the inputs or with antecedent conditions [Beven, 2012]

- 3 **Numerical Dispersion** The effect of numerical approximation in the solution of differential equations in smoothing the pattern of a predicted variable (see Finite Difference, Finite Element Method) [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Nonstationarity** A model in which the parameters are expected to change over time [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Network Width Function** A histogram of the number of reaches in the channel network at a given distance from the catchment outlet. Can be used as the basis for both linear and nonlinear flow routing algorithms [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Nash cascade** Two or more linear reservoirs in series. For a given inflow hydrograph, this conceptual model construct is useful to produce a delayed outflow hydrograph with reduced peak flow that is guaranteed to conserve mass [Ogden, 2020]
- 3 **Neuman Boundary Condition** See Boundary condition
- 3 **Numerical Modelling** The utilisation of a set of mathematical equations solved by means of computational procedures. In principle it should refer to either Dynamical Modelling or Statistical Modelling, but in practice it is more often used as synonymous with the former [Troccoli et al., 2008]
- 3 **Optimisation** The process of finding a parameter set that gives the best fit of a model to the observations available. May be done manually or using an automatic calibration algorithm [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Parameter** A constant that must be defined before running a model simulation [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Physically-based model** A model incorporating measurable internal states (e.g., Capillary Potential) or properties (e.g., Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity).
- 3 **Perceptual Model** A qualitative description of the processes thought to be controlling the hydrological response of an area [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Parameter Space** A space defined by the ranges of feasible model parameters, with one dimension for each parameter [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Parsimony** The concept, sometimes known as Occam's razor, that a model should be no more complex than necessary to predict the observations sufficiently accurately to be useful [Beven, 2012]

- 3 **Partial Area Model** A Perceptual Model **where** infiltration-excess overland flow is only over part of the hillslopes (the partial area) in a catchment [adapted from Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Particle Tracking Models** The representation of water, solute mass, or sediments as a large number of particles that are tracked through a hydrological system according to some rules used to represent the flow processes [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Pedotransfer Function** A function for predicting soil hydraulic parameters (eg Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity) from knowledge of soil texture and other more easily measured variables [Beven, 2012; van Looy et al., 2017]
- 3 **Post-audit Analysis** An evaluation of predictions made of the future behaviour of a system, once the period of predictions has actually occurred [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Quickflow** The component of a storm hydrograph above an arbitrary but fixed separation line; it may be the component of the storm hydrograph linearly related to storm rainfall. Also sometimes called 'direct runoff' or 'stormflow' See Baseflow
- 3 **Raster Digital Elevation Model** A gridded set of elevation values at regular spacing [Beven, 2012]; See Digital Elevation Model
- 3 **Rational Method** An empirical method, first used in the 19th century, for predicting peak discharges based on catchment area and a measure of average rainfall [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Realisation effect** The effect that short periods of observations or stochastic model outputs might lead to different inferences when different periods or different realisations from the stochastic model are used [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Real-Time Forecasting and Updating** Operational forecasting of flows during an event, usually to predict the possibility of flooding, often with adaptive updating of model parameters based on the errors between observed and predicted variables (see also Lead Time) [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Regionalisation** The process of estimating the response of an ungauged catchment using information transferred from gauged catchments [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Relaxation time** The time scale over which the impact of a particular event can be distinguished [Beven, 2012]

- 3 **Residence Time Distributions** The distribution of times that particles have been within a hillslope, channel network or catchment system. There are at least three different uses: to indicate the distribution of times that it takes an increment of input to get to the outlet; to indicate the distribution of times it has taken for the water in an increment of discharge to arrive at the outlet; and to indicate the distribution of times that water has been stored in the system at any given moment. These are all different and should be differentiated (see also Travel Time Distributions) [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Response Surface** The surface defined by the values of an objective function (or other model output variable) as it changes with changes in parameter values. May be thought of conceptually as a surface with “peaks” and “troughs” in the multidimensional space defined by the parameter dimensions, where the peaks represent good fits to the observations and the troughs represent poor fits to the observations (see also Parameter Space) [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Similar Media** A method of scaling the soil moisture characteristics of heterogeneous soils by making assumptions about the structure of the media (e.g. that the geometry of the soil matrix is identical, different only in length scale between different samples) [Beven, 2012]. Also known as 'Miller and Miller (1956) scaling'
- 3 **State Variable** A variable in a model that is part of the solution of the model equations and varies with time during a simulation but which is not a flux or exchange of mass. May include storage and pressure variables, depending on the definition of the model [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Stateful model** A numerical model that keeps track of its state variables and is often run in stand-alone mode [Ogden, 2020]
- 3 **Stateless model** A numerical model that does not keep track of its state, and is often called by another program. Often compiled into a callable library [Ogden, 2020]
- 3 **Stochastic** A model is stochastic if, for a given set of initial and boundary conditions, it may have a range of possible outcomes, often with each outcome associated with an estimated probability [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Steady** Unchanging over time [Ogden, 2020]
- 3 **Streamline** A line following the direction of flow of water in a stream, aquifer or other flow domain [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Stream Tube** The cross-sectional area bounded by surfaces following streamlines in a stream, aquifer or other flow domain [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Superposition** The addition of linear model responses to construct a total response [Beven, 2012]

- 3 **Synthetic storm** A storm obtained by taking a selected value from the frequency curve based on historical series of storm data [NEH, 2012]
- 3 **TopModel** A physically based, variable contributing area model of basin hydrology. Usually a rainfall-runoff model in which distributed predictions of catchment response are made based on a simple theory of hydrological similarity of points in a catchment [Beven and Kirkby, 1979; Beven and Freer, 2001]
- 3 **Top-down Modelling** Using the available observational data to suggest appropriate model structures, usually applied at the catchment scale [Beven, 2012]
Data-Based Mechanistic (DBM) modelling follows such an approach.
- 3 **Tessellation** The discretisation of space into a spatial grid or network of elements [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Transfer Function** A representation of the output from a system due to a unit input [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Triangular Irregular Network** A way of representing topography by a network of triangles between points of known elevation [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Unit Hydrograph** The Quickflow response from a unit of Effective rainfall [adapted from Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Unsteady** Changing with time [Ogden, 2020]
- 3 **Uniform** Not varying in space, the same everywhere [Ogden, 2020]
- 3 **Validation** A process of evaluation of models to confirm that they are acceptable representations of a system. Philosophers of science have some problems with the concept of validation and it may be better to use “Evaluation” or “confirmation” rather than “validation” (which, from its Latin root, implies a degree of truth in the model) [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Vector Digital Elevation Model** A set of irregularly spaced elevation points defining contours of equal elevation [Beven, 2012]
- 3 **Width function** The distribution of the number of streams as a function of distance from the catchment outlet. This function affects the response time distribution of a watershed, which is closely related to its response hydrograph [Ogden, 2020]

Table 4 Statistical analysis

Table	Term, definition and [source]
4	Aleatory Uncertainty Uncertainty due to random variations that can be described by a statistical model [Beven, 2012]
4	Autocorrelated Errors A time series of model residuals that are not independent at each time step, i.e. that exhibit statistical correlation at one or more time steps apart (see also Heteroscedastic Errors) [Beven, 2012]
4	Bayes Equation Equation for calculating a posterior probability given a prior probability and a likelihood function. Used in the GLUE methodology to calculate posterior model likelihood weights from subjective prior weights and a likelihood measure chosen for model evaluation [Beven, 2012]
4	Double Mass Curve A plot of the cumulative volumes associated with two measurement stations (either rainfalls or discharges) [Beven, 2012]
4	Epistemic Uncertainty Uncertainty that is due to lack of knowledge in describing processes or defining input and boundary conditions or to changes in the system over time [Beven, 2012]
4	Fuzzy logic A system of logical rules involving variables associated with a continuous fuzzy measure (normally in the range 0 to 1) rather than the binary measure (right/wrong, 0 or 1) of traditional logic. Rules are available for operations such as addition and multiplication of fuzzy measures and for variables grouped in fuzzy sets. Such rules can be used to reflect imperfect knowledge of how a variable will respond in different circumstances [Beven, 2012]
4	Global optimum A set of parameter values that gives the best fit possible to a set of observations [Beven, 2012]
4	Heteroscedastic Errors A time series of model residuals that exhibit a changing variance over a simulation period (see also Autocorrelated Errors) [Beven, 2012]
4	Likelihood Measure A quantitative measure of the acceptability of a particular model or parameter set in reproducing the hydrological response being modelled [Beven, 2012]
4	Linearity A model is linear if the outputs are in direct proportion to the inputs [Beven, 2012]

- 4 **Local Optimum** A local peak in the parameter response surface where a set of parameter values gives a better fit to the observations than all parameter sets around it, but not as good a fit as the global optimum [Beven, 2012]
- 4 **Model Inadequacy Function** A mathematical function (usually simple in form) designed to correct for non-random structure in a series of model residuals that would otherwise lead to biased inference in model calibration. The simplest correction might be a constant bias or a linear trend [Section 7.3]
- 4 **Nonparametric Method** A method of estimating distributions without making any assumptions about the mathematical form of the distribution [Beven, 2012]
- 4 **Nonstationarity** A model in which the parameters are expected to change over time [Beven, 2012]
- 4 **Objective Function** A measure of how well a simulation fits the available observations [Beven, 2012]
- 4 **Pre-posterior prior analysis** The concept of using predicted variables from a model (with uncertainty) to help design a programme of observations that would lead to the most effective constraint on posterior predictive uncertainty [Beven, 2012]
- 4 **Probability Density Function** A function that describes the probability of the value of a continuous variable being within any interval that must be calculated by integration. For discrete variables the probability is described by a probability mass function [Troccoli et al., 2008]

Table 5 Landscape feature or activity

Table	Term, definition and [source]
5	Afforestation The process of establishing a new forest on land that was not previously forest or land which has not been forest in the recent past. [FC, 2017]
5	Brash bund An embankment built of tree tops, branches and leaves (usually left on forest sites after harvesting) [adapted from FC, 2017]
5	Benefits An additional value to people, places or the economy arising from managing flooding and coastal change [EA, 2020]
5	Biodiversity gain An approach to development that aims to leave the natural environment in a measurably better state than beforehand, by creating or enhancing habitats [EA, 2020]
5	Blue infrastructure Complementary term to ‘green infrastructure’ and includes sustainable drainage systems, swales, wetlands, rivers, canals (and their banks) and other watercourses.
5	Brown earth These are Brown soils (i.e., the Major Soil Group that has a weathered or argillic B horizon and no gleyed subsurface horizon) with a weathered B horizon that is non-calcareous and formed in material other than recent alluvium [Avery, 1980]. The Brown Earth Soil Group is equivalent to the Dystrichrept or Dystric Eutrichrept in the US soil taxonomy and Dystric or Eutric Cambisol in the FAO-UNESCO system [Avery, 1980]. See Soil classification
5	Buffer area or zone A protected or lightly managed area of land designed to separate and buffer the effects of land management activities on the adjacent land, such as helping to intercept, slow and reduce rapid water flow, as well as to capture sediment and associated pollutants. Buffer zones are typically used alongside watercourses to protect the water environment and often managed as unimproved grassland or woodland.
5	Cambisol See Brown earth
5	Channel improvement Where work has been carried out in a river channel to allow an increase in the volume of water it can carry [SEPA, 2020]

- 5 **Continuous Cover Forestry (CCF)** A silvicultural system whereby the forest canopy is maintained at one or more levels without clearfelling [FC, 2017]
- 5 **Contour cultivation** Cultivating the land across the contour to slow down and reduce overland flow within linear cultivation channels, such as plough furrows.
- 5 **Cover crops** Maintaining a vegetation cover within fields over winter (typically grass or clover) to avoid leaving bare soil, to reduce risk of overland flow and soil erosion. [adapted from SEPA, 2015]
- 5 **Cultivation** A method of soil disturbance to aid crop establishment and growth
- 5 **Ecosystem services** The benefits provided by ecosystems that contribute to making human life both possible and worth living, such as clean water.
- 5 **Environmental Land Management (ELM) scheme (England)** A scheme which will replace countryside stewardship and the basic payment scheme after we leave the European Union. Those who are awarded ELM agreements will be paid public money in return for providing environmental benefits [EA, 2020]
- 5 **Environmental net gain** Net gain is an approach to development that aims to leave the natural environment in a measurably better state than beforehand. Net gain is an umbrella term for both biodiversity net gain and wider environmental net gain. The aim of wider environmental net gain is to reduce pressure on and achieve overall improvements in natural capital, ecosystem services and the benefits they deliver [EA, 2020]
- 5 **Floodplain restoration** Actions taken to restore the hydrological connection between rivers and floodplains, so that flood waters inundate the floodplains and store water during times of high flows. This can involve removing flood embankments and other barriers to floodplain connectivity [adapted from EA, 2017]
- 5 **Floodplain storage** Floodplains naturally store water during high flows. Storage can be increased through natural or man-made features to increase flood depth or slow flows in order to reduce flooding elsewhere [SEPA, 2020]
- 5 **Floodplain woodland** All woodland lying within the fluvial floodplain that is subject to intermittent, regular planned or natural flooding regime. It typically comprises broadleaved woodland, and can range from productive woodland on drier, intermittently flooded, areas to unmanaged, native wet woodland in wetter areas [EA, 2017]
- 5 **Forest clearfelling** Cutting down of an area of woodland (if it is within a larger area of woodland it is typically a felling greater than 0.25 hectare). Sometimes a scatter or small clumps of trees may be left standing within the felled area [FC, 2017]

- 5 **Forest plantation** Forests that have been planted or sown and are characterised by intensive silviculture treatment to meet a specific objective or limited range of objectives. Plantations lack most of the characteristics of natural forests [FC, 2017]
- 5 **Forest restocking** Replacing felled areas by sowing seed, planting, or allowing or facilitating natural regeneration [FC, 2017]
- 5 **Forest restructuring** Diversifying the distribution of age classes of a forest, usually by advancing felling in some areas and retarding it in others. Restructuring is usually associated with wider measures to redesign a forest as part of a forest management plan [FC, 2017]
- 5 **Gabion** A metal cage filled with rocks often used in river bank protection [SEPA, 2020]
- 5 **Good arable practices or systems** Practices designed to improve soil structure, such as conservation tillage, early sowing of winter crops or cover crops, crop rotations and tramline management. These act to reduce overland flow, soil compaction and encourage soil water retention [adapted from EA, 2017]
- 5 **Green infrastructure** The use of ecosystems, green spaces and water in strategic land use planning to deliver environmental and quality of life benefits. It includes parks, open spaces, playing fields, woodlands, wetlands, road verges, allotments and private gardens. Green infrastructure can contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, natural disaster risk mitigation, protection against flooding and erosion as well as biodiversity conservation [SEPA, 2020] See Blue infrastructure
- 5 **Habitat Compensation Programme (England)** A national network of regional programmes set up by the Environment Agency to coordinate and oversee habitat creation projects to ensure that the flood and coastal risk management programme meets its legal obligations to habitats and species arising from the Habitats Regulations (2017) [EA, 2020]
- 5 **Hedge** A fence or boundary formed by a dense row of shrubs and/or trees
- 5 **Histosol** See Peat
- 5 **Infiltration basin** A designated area of land that is used to receive overland flow or diverted river water during higher flow periods to recharge deep groundwater
- 5 **Land manager** Any individual or group that manages or controls the use and development of land.

- 5 **Land use planning** The process undertaken by public authorities to identify, evaluate and decide on different options for the use of land, including consideration of long term economic, social and environmental objectives and the implications for different communities and interest groups. [SEPA, 2020]
- 5 **Large woody debris** Pieces of deadwood larger than 100 mm diameter and 1.0 m length, comprising whole trees, logs, branches and root boles that can accumulate within river systems [FC, 2017]
- 5 **Leaky woody structures** Leaky barriers usually consisting of logs and branches, occasionally combined with some living vegetation, that naturally form or can be placed or engineered in river channels, as well as on river banks and across floodplains. Known by a wide range of terms, including leaky woody dams, leaky woody debris dams, large woody dams, coarse woody dams, instream structures, engineered log jams and beaver dams.
- 5 **Livestock poaching** Degradation of soil structure caused by livestock, sometime resulting in soil erosion.
- 5 **Local authority local plan (England)** A plan that sets out the local planning priorities and policies for an area, prepared by the local planning authority (LPA), usually the council or the national park authority [EA, 2020]
- 5 **Local planning authorities (England)** The public authority whose duty it is to carry out specific planning functions for a particular area. All references to local planning authority include the district council, London borough council, county council, Broads Authority, National Park Authority, the Mayor of London and a development corporation, to the extent appropriate to their responsibilities [EA, 2020]
- 5 **Natural capital** The stock of natural assets which include geology, soil, air, water and all living things [EA, 2020]
- 5 **Natural regeneration (woodland)** Plants/trees growing on a site as a result of natural seedfall or suckering. The term is also used to describe the silvicultural practices used to encourage natural seeding and establishment [FC, 2017]
- 5 **Nature-based Solutions (NbS)** These are actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems, that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits [IUCN] Natural Flood Management is one such NbS.
- 5 **Peat** Soils of this Major Soil Group are predominantly organic soils derived for the most part from partially decomposed plant remains that accumulated under waterlogged conditions, either as autochthonous peat in the position of growth or as constituents of sub-aquatic sediments such as organic lake muds; soils consisting of organic materials that have been artificially displaced are also included. They are required to have 1/ more than 40 cm of organic material (O horizon) material within the upper 80 cm, excluding fresh litter (L) and living moss; or 2/ more than 30 cm of organic (O horizon) material resting directly on bedrock (R or Cr) or extremely stoney material; and 3/ no overlying non-humose mineral horizon that has a colour value of 4 or more and extends below 30 cm depth [Avery, 1980]. The Podzol Major Soil Group is equivalent to the Histosol class in the US soil taxonomy and FAO-UNESCO system [Avery, 1980]. See Soil classification

- 5 **Peatland restoration** Interventions designed to re-wet and restore peatland vegetation on drained and damaged peatland sites, including forested peatlands. Can include grip/drain blocking and gully blocking to raise water-tables, and reseeded or the use of sphagnum 'plugs' to aid natural revegetation.
- 5 **Podzol** Soils of this Major Soil Group have a podzolic B horizon; while the Podzol Soil Group specifically also has an albic E (Ea) horizon not qualifying as a bleached hardpan, a prominent Bh horizon with coated grains, or both, and no thin ironpan or gleyed subsurface horizon [Avery, 1980]. The Podzol Soil Group is equivalent to the Orthod or Humod Groups in the US soil taxonomy and Humic or Orthic Podzols in the FAO-UNESCO system [Avery, 1980]. See Soil classification
- 5 **Ponds** Small bodies of standing water that may contribute to flood storage depending on the management of water levels and available 'freeboard'.
- 5 **Regulated tidal exchange** Similar to managed realignment except that instead of the removal of breaches or a bank, flow control structures such as culverts, sluices and tidal gates are used to control the ingress and egress of water into and out of a defined area of coast line. [EA, 2017]
- 5 **Revetment** Sloping structures placed on banks or at the foot of cliffs in such a way as to deflect the energy of incoming water [SEPA, 2020]
- 5 **Rewilding** Rewilding is an approach that works with natural processes to restore ecosystems [Rewilding Britain, 2016]
- 5 **Riparian** The riparian area is the interface between land and a river or stream. It commonly refers to the riparian owner, which denotes ownership of the land area beside a river or stream. [SEPA, 2020]
- 5 **Riparian landowners** People who own a stretch of watercourse that runs on or under their land; or is on the boundary of their land, up to its centre. Riparian landowners have legal responsibilities for the stretch of watercourse they own [EA, 2020]
- 5 **Riparian woodland** Woodland located within the riparian zone, defined here as the land immediately adjoining a watercourse or standing water and influenced by it (which includes the river bank but not the wider floodplain). Usually relatively narrow and typically comprises native broadleaved woodland [adapted from EA, 2017]
- 5 **River bank restoration** The protection and stabilisation of river banks by a range of natural or engineered techniques (e.g. fencing, tree planting or the use of revetment and gabions) to reduce erosion, bank collapse and siltation.
- 5 **River restoration** The reinstatement of the natural physical processes (e.g. renaturalising flow and sediment supply regimes by removing weirs) and features (e.g. adding wood, altering river shape and introducing sediment gravel) that are characteristic of a river, with the aim of increasing hydraulic roughness, slowing river flows and enhancing temporary water storage by reconnecting rivers with their floodplains [EA, 2017]

- 5 **Runoff attenuation features** The construction of features that mimic natural hydrological regimes to minimise the impact of human activity on surface water drainage discharge, reducing flooding and pollution of waterways and groundwater. They include measures such as swales, ponds and sediment traps [EA, 2017]
- 5 **Sediment fence** A geotextile barrier placed across a overland flow pathway to intercept, filter and trap sediment. Typically used as a short-term intervention for pollution control.
- 5 **Sediment management** Covers a wide range of activities that includes anything from the small scale removal of dry gravels to the dredging of whole river channels and the reintroduction of removed sediment into the water environment. Historically, sediment management has been carried out for several reasons, including reducing flood risk, reducing bank erosion, for use as aggregate and to improve land drainage [SEPA, 2020]
- 5 **Sediment trap** An excavated area of ground located on an overland flow pathway designed to slow the flow of water and promote settlement and trapping of sediment.
- 5 **Short Rotation Coppice (SRC)** Trees (usually willow or poplar) typically grown as an energy crop and harvested at intervals of about three years [FC, 2017]
- 5 **Short Rotation Forestry (SRF)** The practice of growing single or multi-stemmed trees of fast-growing species on a reduced rotation length primarily for the production of biomass [FC,2017]
- 5 **Soil aeration** The use of tractor mounted equipment to break up topsoil compaction and aerate the soil. This can involve the use of long spikes or the removal of small soil cores [EA, 2017]
- 5 **Soil association** Soil map units that include significant proportions of contrasting kinds of soil, or in which a single dominant class (eg Soil Group) cannot be predicted reliably from available data [Avery, 1980]. Soil Associations are named after the most extensive Soil Series, though no one series may dominate [Jarvis et al., 1984]. There are 296 Soil Associations covering England and Wales, and these mapping units are further simplified into 27 LandIS® Soilscape classes. See Soil classification
- 5 **Soil classification** The principal classification of soils in England and Wales, on the basis of diagnostic properties, is the Soil Group e.g., Brown Earth [Avery, 1980]. Soils may be further distinguished in a Soil Subgroup eg Typical Brown Earth, and further separated into Soil Series using additional diagnostic properties and parent material e.g. Denbigh Series [Clayden and Hollis, 1984; Jarvis et al., 1984]. See also Soil Association
- 5 **Soilscape classification** See Soil association
- 5 **Soil series** See Soil classification

- 5 **Soil texture** The proportion of a soil horizon that is composed of clay-sized particles, silt-sized particles and sand-sized particles.
- 5 **Soil type** See Soil classification
- 5 **Subsoiling** The use of a tractor mounted implement such as a winged tine to lift, loosen and break up the subsoil to improve vertical drainage.
- 5 **Strategic environmental assessment (SEA)** An assessment undertaken to ensure that the environment is considered during the development of a plan or strategy. It helps to ensure environmental issues are fully integrated into the plan making process alongside technical, economic and other factors. In doing so it can contribute to the promotion of sustainable development and environmental protection. [EA, 2020]
- 5 **Surficial geology** The surficial geology, also referred to as Quaternary geology, refers to those unconsolidated geologic materials lying on top of the Solid geology or bedrock.
- 5 **Sustainable forest management** The stewardship and use of forests and forest lands in a way, and at a rate, that maintains their biodiversity, productivity, regeneration capacity and vitality and their potential to fulfil, now and in the future, relevant ecological, economic and social functions at local, national and global levels, and that does not cause damage [FC, 2017]
- 5 **Swale** Shallow, broad and vegetated channel designed to store and/or convey overland flow and remove pollutants
- 5 **Vegetation planting** Planting by seed, plugs or turf to promote revegetation of bare ground or to alter vegetation cover [EA, 2017]
- 5 **Washlands** See offline storage areas
- 5 **Wetland creation** The construction of a wetland on a non-wetland site such as by shallow excavation, damming or diverting water flows, and importing materials
- 5 **Wetlands** Transitional areas between wet and dry environments: they range from permanently or intermittently wet land to shallow water and water margins. The term can describe marshes, swamps and bogs, some shallow waters and the intertidal zone. When applied to surface waters, it is generally restricted to areas shallow enough to allow the growth of rooted plants [FC, 2017]

- 5 **Woodland** The term 'woodland' is used to describe land predominantly covered in trees (with a canopy cover of at least 20%), whether in large tracts (generally called forests) or smaller areas known by a variety of terms, including woods, copses, spinneys or shelterbelts.
- 5 **Woodland creation** Tree planting to create a new woodland
- 5 **Woodland (cross-slope woodland)** Smaller areas or belts of woodland across hill slopes [EA, 2017]
- 5 **Woodland establishment** The formative period which ends after young trees are of sufficient size so that, given adequate protection, they are likely to survive as woodland at the required stocking density [FC, 2017]

Table 6 UK flood risk management

Table	Term, definition and [source]
6	<p>Benefit-Cost Ratio Economic statistic summarising the overall value for money of an action or project. It is expressed as the ratio of benefits to costs (both expressed as present value monetary values). A ratio of greater than 1:1 indicates that the economic benefits associated with an action are greater than the economic costs of implementation; therefore this is taken as the threshold of economic viability [SEPA, 2020]</p>
6	<p>Build back better Re-building properties, businesses and infrastructure after a flood or coastal change event in a way which reduces future damages and improves resilience, rather than putting back what was there before [EA, 2020]</p>
6	<p>Catchment based approach Planning, integrating and implementing Natural Flood Management (NFM) and other positive environmental measures at a catchment scale to reduce downstream flood risk.</p>
6	<p>Communities at risk data Indicative flood risk areas derived for the Environment Agency's communities at risk approach [EA, 2020]</p>
6	<p>Community Flood Action Groups (FLAGs) Community-based resilience groups which, on behalf of local residents and business, help to prepare for and minimise the effects of flooding. They reflect the interests of their local communities and may differ in composition and remit [SEPA, 2020]</p>
6	<p>Cost-effective The option that reduces flooding and or coastal change for the least overall cost [EA, 2020]</p>
6	<p>Demountable defences A temporary flood barrier that is only installed when the need arises, that is, when flooding is forecast. A demountable flood defence is a particular type of temporary defence that requires built-in parts and therefore can only be deployed in one specific location.</p>
6	<p>Drainage and sewerage management plans (England) Plans produced by water companies setting out how they intend to extend, improve and maintain a robust and resilient drainage and wastewater system. [EA, 2020]</p>
6	<p>Flash flood A flood that occurs a short period of time after high intensity rainfall or a sudden snow melt. A sudden increase in the level and velocity of the water body is often characteristic of these events, leaving a short time for warning or actions [SEPA, 2020]</p>
6	<p>Flood and coastal erosion risk management (FCERM) Managing the risks of flooding and coastal erosion to people, property and the natural environment through minimising, predicting and managing the risk [EA, 2020]</p>

- 6 **Flood bund** A constructed retaining wall, embankment or dyke designed to protect against flooding to a specified standard of protection.
- 6 **Flood damages** Direct damage to buildings and contents caused by flood water, or indirect damage resulting from the consequential loss of industrial production, travel disruption or stress and anxiety. Some damages can be quantified in monetary terms, and others can only be described [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood Defence** Infrastructure intended to protect an area against flooding, to a specified standard of protection. Can include flood and sea walls and embankments, pumping stations, upstream flood storage areas, natural features like river channels, as well as structures like sluices, harbour walls, trash screens or culverts. Sometimes structures and features that are not traditionally considered to be a defence also help to manage flood risk and coastal change. For example bridges, garden walls and buildings [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Floods Directive** European Directive 2007/60/EC on the assessment and management of flood risks that builds on and is closely related to the Water Framework Directive (see river basin management planning). The Directive requires Member States to assess if all watercourses and coastlines are at risk from flooding, to map the flood extent, assets and humans at risk in these areas and to take adequate and coordinated measures to reduce this flood risk [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood embankment** Engineered earthfill structure designed to contain high river levels or protect against coastal flooding. They are commonly grass-covered, but may need additional protection against erosion by swiftly flowing water, waves or overtopping [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood extent** The area that has been affected by flooding, or is at risk of flooding from one or more sources for a particular likelihood.
- 6 **Flood gate** An adjustable, sometimes temporary, barrier used as a flood defence to control the flow of water within a water system or during a flood. Flood gates can also be part of operational flood defences or protect individual buildings or sites [SEPA,2020]
- 6 **Flood guard** A variety of types of door and window barriers that can be fitted to individual properties and operated by the owners/occupiers prior to a flood event. They act as a physical barrier to water entering the property and can provide protection against frequent and relatively shallow flooding [SEPA,2020]
- 6 **Flood hazard** The hazard arising from the depth, extent and speed of floodwater.
- 6 **Flood hazard map** Map showing information that describes the nature of a flood in terms of the source, extent, water level or depth and, where appropriate, velocity of water [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood investment** The funding of flood and coastal defences and maintenance of river channels. Also refers to funding or improving other measures such as natural flood management, and the preparedness to help communities recover after a flooding or coastal event [EA, 2020]

- 6 **Flood maintenance** Duties of watercourse inspection, clearance and repair on local authorities. In addition, local authorities may also be responsible for maintenance of existing flood protection schemes or defences [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood mitigation** Management and control of flooding to reduce potential damages.
- 6 **Flood prevention/protection scheme** A scheme by a local authority for the management of flood risk within the authority area, including defence measures [SEPA,2020]
- 6 **Flood protection** Defence against flooding when it occurs.
- 6 **Flood protection works** The same flood defence measures that would make up a formal Flood Protection Scheme but without the legal process, protections and requirements that would come by delivering the works as a scheme [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood resilience** The capacity of people and places to plan for, better protect, respond to, and to recover from flooding and coastal change. Places can achieve this by: making the best land use and development choices, better protecting people and places, responding to and recovering from flooding and coastal change whilst all the time adapting to climate change [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood risk** A measure of the combination of the likelihood of flooding occurring and the associated impacts on people, the economy and the environment [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood risk assessment** Detailed studies of an area where flood risk may be present. These are often used to inform planning decisions, may help to develop flood schemes and can contribute to a National Flood Risk Assessment [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood Risk Management (Scotland) Act 2009** The flood risk management legislation for Scotland. It transposes the EC Floods Directive into Scots Law and aims to reduce the adverse consequences of flooding on communities, the environment, cultural heritage and economic activity [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood risk management cycle** Under the Floods Directive flood risk management planning is undertaken in six year cycles. The first planning cycle is 2015 – 2021. The first delivery cycle is lagged by approximately 6 months and is from 2016-2022.
- 6 **Flood risk management local advisory groups (Scotland)** Stakeholder groups convened to advise SEPA and lead local authorities in the preparation of Flood Risk Management Plans. SEPA and lead local authorities must have regard to the advice they provide.

- 6 **Flood risk management plans (FRMPs)** Plans that explain the risk of flooding from rivers, the sea, surface water, groundwater and reservoirs. They also set out how risk management authorities will work with communities and take actions to manage flood risk over the next 6 years [EA, 2020].
- 6 **Flood risk management strategy** A long-term vision for the overall reduction of flood risk. They contain a summary of the flood risk, together with information on catchment characteristics and a summary of objectives and actions [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood risk map** Complements the flood hazard map by providing detail on the impacts of flooding on people, the economy and the environment [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood Risk Regulations (2009)** Regulations which transpose the European Floods Directive (2007) into UK law. The aim of the regulations is to reduce the likelihood and consequence of flooding [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood vulnerability** A measure of how likely someone or something is to suffer long-term damage as a result of flooding. It is a combination of the likelihood of suffering harm or damage during a flood (susceptibility) and the ability to recover following a flood (resilience) [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Flood wall** A flood defence feature used to defend an area from flood water to a specified standard of protection [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Freeboard** The vertical distance between the top of a runoff retention feature and the normal water level. This defines the available storage capacity of the feature to hold flood water during a high flow event.
- 6 **Groundwater flooding** This type of flooding is caused by water rising up from underlying rocks or flowing from springs [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Gully blocking** Using a range of materials (including wood, plastic, stone and heather) to block gullies formed by erosion and overland flow, typically within peatlands, to create temporary flood storage [adapted from EA, 2017]
- 6 **Headwater management (EA term)** Amending the design of paths, tracks, roads and associated ditches to slow overland flow and enhance water storage during storm events. Can include a range of interventions, including the use of permeable paving, gutters, cambers, crossfalls and culverts, which can split, spread and discharge water to buffer areas.
- 6 **Integrated catchment management** A holistic approach to managing catchment inputs and outputs, combining land and water management.
- 6 **Internal drainage board (IDB)** A public body that manages water levels in an area, known as an internal drainage district. IDBs undertake works to reduce flood risk to people and property, and manage water levels for agricultural and environmental needs within their district [EA, 2020]

- 6 **Land Management Measures or Interventions (SEPA term)** Land based techniques and practices that seek to influence flood generation by reducing the amount of surface runoff reaching the river network. They achieve this primarily by improving soil structure, increasing infiltration, and ultimately increasing the capacity of the land to store water. Examples include a change in a land management practice, construction of a run-off attenuation feature, planting of a new woodland and managed realignment on the coast [SEPA, 2015]
- 6 **Lead Local Authority (Scotland)** A local authority responsible for leading the production, consultation, publication and review of a Local Flood Risk Management Plan [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Lead Local Flood Authority (England)** Local authorities in England responsible for developing, maintaining and applying a strategy for local floodrisk management in their areas and for maintaining a register of flood risk assets [Defra, 2014]
- 6 **Local Flood Risk Management Plans (Scotland)** Plans produced by lead local authorities to take forward the objectives and actions set out in Flood Risk Management Strategies. They will provide detail on the funding, timeline of delivery, arrangements and co-ordination of actions at the local level during each six year FRM planning cycle [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Local flood strategies (England)** Statutory strategies developed by lead local flood authorities which sets out how they plan to manage the local flood risk (surface water, ordinary watercourses and groundwater flooding) in their area. [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Local resilience forum (England)** Multi-agency partnerships made up of representatives from local public services, including the emergency services, local authorities, the NHS, the Environment Agency and others. These agencies are known as Category 1 Responders, as defined by the Civil Contingencies Act [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Long-term investment scenarios (LTIS)** Long-term investment scenarios for flood and coastal erosion risk management. New climate change, population and mapping data are used to set out potential future scenarios, assessing the costs and benefits of long-term investment to meet these challenges. Evidence which government and others use to consider future policy and investment choices [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Main river (England)** Rivers which are shown on the Main River Map. They are usually the larger rivers and streams. The Environment Agency may carry out maintenance, improvement or construction work on main rivers to manage flood risk. Other rivers not on the Main River Map are called 'ordinary watercourses' [EA, 2020]
- 6 **National Flood Forum** A national charity which supports individuals and communities at risk of flooding [EA, 2020]
- 6 **National Flood Risk Assessment** A national analysis of flood risk from all sources of flooding which also considers climate change impacts [SEPA, 2020]

- 6 **Natural flood management (NFM)** The use of natural processes to reduce the risk of flooding or coastal change [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Natural flood management measures** Individual techniques or interventions that are used to reduce the amount or rate of rapid water flow and/or improve the ability of rivers and their floodplains to manage flood water [adapted from SEPA, 2015]
- 6 **Objective Target Area (Scotland)** Priority areas for managing flood risk within Potentially Vulnerable Areas
- 6 **Offline storage areas** Areas on the floodplain that have been adapted to retain and attenuate floodwater in a managed way. They usually require the construction of a containment bund which increases the amount of water that can be stored and may also require an inlet, outlet and potentially a spillway mechanism. Known by a variety of terms, including waslands (larger-scale) and runoff attenuation features (smaller-scale) [EA, 2017]
- 6 **Offline storage ponds** Storage of flood flow from the river in offline ponds – ponds adjacent to the watercourse designed to reduce flood peaks downstream by physically storing some of the flow and slowing the rate of the flood peak downstream [adapted from EA, 2011]
- 6 **Online storage ponds** Storage of flood flow from the river in online ponds – ponds on the course of the river designed to reduce flood peaks downstream by physically storing some of the flow and slowing the rate of the flood peak downstream [adapted from EA, 2011]
- 6 **Ordinary watercourses (England)** A watercourse that does not form part of a main river and is not shown on the main river map. Lead local flood authorities, district councils and internal drainage boards may carry out flood risk management work on ordinary watercourses [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Partnership funding** Defra’s current policy which provides a system of funding that applies to all flood & coastal erosion risk management projects seeking central government funding in England. The main objectives of partnership funding is to offer communities the opportunity to invest in (and benefit from) local flood and coastal erosion risk management measures, that could not be afforded from central government funding alone [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Potentially Vulnerable Areas (Scotland)** Catchments identified as being at risk of flooding and where the impact of flooding is sufficient to justify further assessment and appraisal [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Property flood resilience (PFR)** Measures people can take to help keep flood water out of their home or business; or limit the damage if it does. Examples include flood gates over doors, tiled floors or raised plug sockets [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Property level protection** Includes flood gates, sandbags and other temporary barriers that can be used to prevent water from entering individual properties during a flood [SEPA, 2020]

- 6 **Regional flood and coastal committees (England)** Committees which were established by the Environment Agency under the Flood and Water Management Act 2010 to bring together members appointed by government, the Environment Agency and lead local flood authorities [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Residual risk** The risk which remains after risk management and mitigation. This may include risk due to very severe (above design standard) storms or risks from unforeseen hazards [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Responsible Authority (Scotland)** Authorities designated under the Flood Risk Management (Scotland) Act 2009 and associated legislation, including local authorities, Scottish Water, the National Park Authorities and Scottish Forestry. Responsible authorities, along with SEPA and Scottish Ministers, have specific duties in relation to their flood risk related functions [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **River basin management plans (RBMPs)** Plans, developed by the Environment Agency, which set out how organisations, stakeholders and communities will work together to improve the water environment [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Standard of Protection** All flood protection structures are designed to be effective up to a specified flood likelihood (Standard of Protection). For events beyond this standard, flooding will occur. The chosen Standard of Protection will determine the required defence height and/or capacity [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Strategic Flood Risk Assessment** The collection, analysis and presentation of all existing and readily available flood risk information for the area of interest. It constitutes a strategic overview of flood risk [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Structural measure** For flood prevention work, any form of earthwork dam, ditch, levee, drop spillway, jetties, riprap, etc., or installation of concrete, masonry, metal, or other material (NEH, 2012]
- 6 **Surcharge** Watercourses and culverts can carry a limited amount of water. When they can no longer cope, they overflow, or 'surcharge' [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS)** Approaches to manage surface water that take account of water quantity (flooding), water quality (pollution) biodiversity (wildlife and plants) and amenity are collectively referred to as Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS)
- 6 **Surface Water Management Action Plan** A plan that takes an integrated approach to managing the risk of surface water flooding, accounting for all aspects of urban drainage systems and produces long term and sustainable actions. The aim is to ensure that during a flood the flows created can be managed in a way that will cause minimum harm to people, buildings, the environment and business [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Sustainable drainage systems (SuDS)** Approaches to manage surface water that take account of water quantity (flooding), water quality (pollution), biodiversity (wildlife and plants) and amenity [EA, 2020]

- 6 **Sustainable flood risk management** An approach to managing flood risk that aims to meet human needs, whilst preserving the environment so that these needs can be met not only in the present, but also for future generations. The delivery of sustainable development is generally recognised to reconcile three pillars of sustainability – environmental, social and economic [SEPA, 2020]
- 6 **Waterbody** A unit of surface water, being the whole (or part) of a stream, river or canal, lake or reservoir, estuary or stretch of coastal water. A groundwater water body is a defined area of an aquifer with geological and hydrological boundaries to ensure consistency and avoid fragmentation [EA, 2020]
- 6 **Whole-catchment approach** See catchment based approach.
- 6 **Working with Natural Processes** Taking action to manage fluvial and coastal flood and coastal erosion risk by protecting, restoring and emulating the natural regulating function of catchments, rivers, floodplains and coasts.

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